

CULTURE-ORIENTED APPROACHES TO FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHING

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***Abstract** In the context of the development of integration and globalization processes in modern language education, there is a need for the development of a personality prepared for the effective implementation of intercultural communication, considering the fact that language and culture are in the closest connection and joint study of language and culture is an important condition for mastering a foreign language. This article is devoted to the study of culture-oriented approaches used in the process of teaching a foreign language. It describes the descriptions and principles, of culture-oriented approaches. Features and purposes of the considered approaches are also viewed. The analysis of the culture-oriented approaches to teaching a foreign language used in teaching allows us to conclude that the development of culture in the process of learning a foreign language is of great interest in linguodidactics.*

***Keywords:** Methodology, approach, culture-oriented, linguo-country study, linguocultural, sociocultural, intercultural, linguodidactics.*

Integrating culture into the system of teaching a foreign language is one of the fundamental issue in the methodology of teaching foreign languages. “Foreign language teaching is beginning to change in recognition of the need for intercultural communicative competence” [1]. If we compare two national cultures, we can conclude that they never completely coincide. This follows from the fact that each consists of national and international elements. For each culture, the combination of these elements will be different. According to linguist S.G. Ter-Minasova, “every lesson of a foreign language is a crossroads of cultures, it is a practice of intercultural

communication, because every foreign word reflects a foreign world and a foreign culture: behind every word there is an idea of the world conditioned by national consciousness” [2]. Today, the concept of teaching language and culture in their inseparable connection is generally recognized. It has found its embodiment both in normative educational regulations and in a variety of scientific concepts that seek to identify special vectors of interaction of language and culture in the process of foreign language teaching.

As a result of a special interest in the identified issues in the science of teaching a foreign language, various approaches have arisen aimed at substantiating linguodidactic strategies based on the interaction of language and culture in the educational process. Presently, a large amount of information has been accumulated on culture-oriented approaches. “In the foreign theory and practice of language teaching, significant experience has been accumulated in the formation of a competent specialist in a foreign language, a system of approaches and methods has been developed that contribute to the effective teaching of a foreign language” [3]. The implementation of the idea of teaching a foreign language and culture in linguodidactics is promoted by culture-oriented approaches. In linguodidactics there are such approaches as linguo-country study, linguocultural, sociocultural, sociolinguistic, multicultural, and intercultural. Besides them, such approaches as functional-semantic, cultural-sensitive, transcultural, ethnographic are being studied.

The linguo-country study approach. One of the first concepts in the theory and methodology of teaching foreign languages that integrate language and culture into a single linguo-educational space is considered to be the theory of the linguo-country study approach. It is integrating language and culture into a single linguo-educational space. V. G. Kostomarov and E. M. Vereshchagin are considered to be the pioneers of linguo-country study in Russia. “Linguistic and cultural material not only contains information about a linguistic fact, but, most importantly, helps the

student of a foreign language to understand the national historical features of this fact - the features of a different socioculture” [4]. Mastering a foreign language is impossible without studying the culture of the country. The need to possess extensive knowledge about the specifics of the country of the language being studied has made the linguistic and country study component one of the most important in teaching a foreign language. The formation of linguo-country study and sociocultural knowledge, the study of the national cultural semantics of words, background vocabulary and phraseological units, the verbal behavior of representatives of the target language in communication, improving of knowledge about the country of the target language and its culture is an essential component of the linguo-country study approach.

The principles of the linguo-country study approach are as follows:

- knowledge about the realities of the country of the language being studied and the ways of their expression in the language, lexical and phraseological units.

The linguocultural approach is a linguocultural teaching strategy that aims to enrich students with knowledge in the field of the system of cultural values expressed in the language. “The most important task of linguoculture (linguoculturology) and its characteristic distinctive feature is the systemic representation of the culture of the people in their language ...” [5].

There are following principles of the linguocultural approach:

- the relationship and mutual influence of language and culture and the interpretation of this interaction;
- the study of spiritual and material culture, which forms the "linguistic picture of the world";
- knowledge of the system of cultural concepts and values expressed in the language;
- analysis of language units with a national cultural component of meaning, stereotypes of speech behavior.

The sociocultural approach developed by Safonova V.V. is associated not only with the concept of national culture, but also with the social aspect and stereotypes of everyday life. This approach takes culture as a wide range of social phenomena that are the result of the development and function of a particular society. Sociocultural theories draw on the work of Lev Vygotsky, who posits that “learning occurs through social interactions, as learners make meaning through the negotiation of new concepts (and language)” [6].

The principles of the sociocultural approach are as follows:

- humanization and cultural sociologization of the content of foreign language education;
- development of the student's personality as a cultural and historical subject, a carrier of socio-cultural characteristics;
- development of socio-cultural competence;
- use of a system of problematic sociocultural tasks;
- reliance on the analysis of the language learning environment and socio-cultural characteristics of languages and cultures.

The intercultural approach. When learning a foreign language and appropriating the features of someone else's behavior, the student expands his/her picture of the world in two directions. Simultaneously with the acquiring the knowledge and abilities in the field of a foreign language, s/he is aware of the features of his native language and his own culture, which are still not realized, since they were appropriated in the early phases of socialization. A foreign language and culture act as a mirror that reflects the unconscious features of the native language and one's own culture. Thus, the student's picture of the world develops due to the comprehension of both another and his own culture; this provides the possibility of secondary socialization in the course of intercultural interaction. As Kramsch states “a foreign culture and one's own culture should be placed together in order for learners to understand a foreign culture”. She defines this as establishing “a sphere

of interculturality” [7]. The intercultural strategy of teaching foreign languages assumes an equal position of two cultures participating in intercultural communication. The equality of native and foreign culture is the main component of the intercultural approach, where the study of culture occurs through the study of language, since one of the key functions of the language is the preservation, development and transmission of culture. “The language and cultural diversity are dealt with as value elements of the world cultural heritage and the philosophy of intercultural social interaction in any multilingual and polycultural space” [8].

Here are the following principles of the intercultural approach:

- cultural awareness;
- availability of cultural background knowledge;
- comparison of two or more cultures;
- reliance on the analysis of various situations of communication, the identification of general and specific;
- equal relations between native and other cultures.

It should be recognized that the culture-oriented approaches functioning in the context of linguodidactics form a single system, coordinating with each other as orientation in teaching culturally-significant factors of communication.

From a brief review of the existing concepts, we can conclude that the culture-oriented approaches included in the thesaurus of linguistics, as a whole, are a fairly harmonious scientific area with their subject and object specifics. A common feature of these approaches is the cooperation of the studied language and culture in the learning process. Based on the study of culture-oriented approaches to foreign language teaching, the development of culture-oriented approaches demonstrates the critical importance of language and culture in foreign language teaching, and they should be considered to be more effective among other approaches.

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